

“Preliminary notes on the forms of Old Chinese qualitative ablaut”

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1. **Some arguments for investigating Old Chinese vowel alternations**
- 1.1 Vowel alternations with morphological functions reported for the following branches of Tibeto-Burman
 - Bodic (SIMON 1949-50, 1974-75, DURR 1950, HAHN 1973, SPRIGG 1980)
 - Stau (HUANG BÜFÁN 1990)
 - Ergong and Muya (SŪN HÒNGKĀI 1996, XŪ SHÌXUÁN 1996)
 - various Kiranti languages (VAN DRIEM 1987, 1990, 1992, 1993. a,b)
 - Tangut (GŌNG HUÁNGCHÉNG 1989, 1990)
 - Qiang (SŪN HÒNGKĀI 1981, 1996)
 - Primi (LŪ SHÀOZŪN 1983)
 - Trung (SŪN HÒNGKĀI 1982)
 - Tsangla, Takpa, Kaman, Taraon (SŪN HÒNGKĀI et al. 1980, LŪ SHÀOZŪN 1988)
 - Garhwal-Jad (SHARMA 1994).
- 1.2 Ablaut reconstructed as part of shared Tibeto-Burman morphology by SHAFER (1940-41) and MILLER (1957, 1958)
- 1.3 Tonal based ablaut system existing in Yenisseian (WERNER & SCHABLO 1978), a language family assumed to be cognate with Sino-Tibetan by one author (STAROSTIN 1984)
- 1.4 Ablaut systems assumed to be an old “Eurasianic” areal trait (GREENBERG 1989)
- 1.5 Main vowel alternations in etymologically related Old Chinese word families recognized already by Qing philologists; cf. YÁO RÓNGSŌNG (1991), RĒN JĪFĀNG (1992) for examples
- 1.6 Old Chinese close/open alternation in a 2-vowel system assumed to correspond to a regular semantic “extrovert/introvert” dichotomy, closely akin to the system of Indo-European ablaut and NW-Caucasian vowel alternation (PULLEYBLANK 1965. a,b, 1972. a,b, 1989, 1993, 1995, 1996, cf. also PALMATTIS 1979 on IE, JAKOVLEV 1942 on NWC)
- 1.7 Old Chinese vowel alternations in reduplicated and expressive compounds (mainly *e ⇨ o, *i ⇨ u; also *e ⇨ a, *i ⇨ a; see ZHŌU FĀGĀO 1962: 96-201, BAXTER & SAGART 1998: 65-66; cf. also BAO ZHIMING 1996 for an analysis of the Middle Chinese situation) confirm to generalized theory of “apophonic path” (SÉGERAL & SCHEER (1996, Ms.:26-27); universality of mechanism in expressives first noticed by GRAMMONT (1933); similar formations presumed to be a SEA areal phenomenon (WILLIAMS 1991) or Sino-Tibetan inheritance (YŪ MÍN 1992)

2. Old Chinese initial classes

- I. LABIALS (*p-, *pʰ-, *b-, *m-, *hm-)
- II. DENTALS (*t-, *tʰ-, *d-, *n-, *hn-)
- III. LATERALS (*l-, *hl-), RHOTICS (*r-, *hr-)
- IV. SIBILANTS (*ts-, *tsʰ-, *dz-, *s-)
- V. VELARS & LARYNGEALS (*k-, *kʰ-, *g-, *ŋ-, *hŋ-, *x-, *ʔ-)
- VI. LABIOVELARS & LABIOLARYNGEALS (*kʷ-, *kʰʷ-, *gʷ-, *ŋʷ-, *hŋʷ-, *w-, *hʷ-, *xʷ-, *ʔʷ-)

2.1 Complete distribution of initials throughout A ⇔ E-type ablaut*

2.1.1

LABIALS

(*p-, *ph-, *b-, *m-, *hm-, w-)

- | | | | |
|-----|---|---|---|
| (1) | <i>bó</i> (782I) 伯博陌切，幫陌入二開
M. <i>pæk</i> (E. *paik) < O. *ʔp-r-ak
“elder, father’s eldest brother; chief, count” | ⇔ | <i>bì</i> (853a) 辟必益切，幫昔入三開
M. <i>bjiek</i> (E. *pjiajk) < O. *ʔpek
“ruler, prince; to ward off” |
| (2) | <i>fāng</i> (740t) 訪敷亮切，敷漾去三合
M. <i>phjaŋH</i> (E. *pʰuaŋʰ) < O. *ʔpʰang-s
“ask after, inquire, pay a visit” | ⇔ | <i>pín/gǐ</i> (839d) 聘匹政切，滂勁去三開
M. <i>phjengH</i> (E. *phjiajŋʰ) < O. *ʔpʰeŋ-s
“go to inquire, invite; seek a marriage” |
| (3) | <i>páng</i> (740b) 旁步光切，並唐平一開
M. <i>bang</i> (E. *ban) < O. *ʔbaŋ
“side” | ⇔ | <i>bìng</i> (840ab) 並 蒲迴切，並迴上四開
M. <i>beng</i> (E. *bejŋʰ) < O. *ʔbeŋ-ʔ
“side by side, equally, together” |
| (4) | <i>máng</i> (742q) 盲武庚切，明庚平二開
M. <i>mæŋ</i> (E. *maiŋ) < O. *ʔm-r-aŋ
“blind” | ⇔ | <i>míng</i> (841b) 冥莫經切，明青平四開
M. <i>meng</i> (E. *mejŋ) < O. *ʔmeŋ
“be dizzy; close eyes” |
| (5) | <i>hū</i> (103o) 瞋荒烏切，曉模平一合
M. <i>xu</i> (E. *muaʰ) < O. *ʔhma
“big slice of minced meat” | ⇔ | <i>xī</i> (124Ii) 醯呼雞切，曉齊平四開
M. <i>xej</i> (E. *xej) < O. *ʔhme
“minced food in vinegar” |

*) ABBREVIATIONS: *H* = page number & column (*l, m, n*) in *Hanyǐ dà zìdiǎn* 漢語大字典 — *M* = entry no. in Morohashi Tetsuji’s *Dai kanwa jiten* 大漢和辭典 — *M.* = Middle Chinese *transcription* according to Baxter (1992) — *O.* = Old Chinese reconstruction according to Baxter (1992), with emendations proposed in Baxter (1995 a,b), Sagart (1997/98, Ms, partly) — *E.* = Early Middle Chinese reconstruction according to Pulleyblank (1984, 1991, 1994, 1995) — **釋** = reading from the *Jiyun* 集韻 — **a* = Type A-prosody syllable / **b* = Type B-prosody syllable according to the rhyme table tradition — ^A = Type A-prosody syllable of the segregating series (GSR nos. 18, 178, 185, 351, 609, 627, 766, 855, 978, 1015, 1055, 1114, 1125, 1193) — ^B = Type B-prosody syllable of the segregating series (GSR nos. 69, 76, 123, 475, 502, 613, 655, 668, 669, 694, 755, 1032, 1069) according to Sagart (1997/98, Ms.), ⇔ = stands in ablaut relationship of unspecified directionality)

2.1.2 DENTALS

(*t-, *th-, *d-, *n-, *hn-)

- (6) *dǎn* (H 1974^r) 𦉑都感切，端敢上一開
 M. *tan*X (E.*tam') < O.*^ham-ʔ (? < *k-l-)
 “dirt; black; tattoo”
 ⇔ *diǎn* (618n) 𦉑多忝切，端忝上四開
 M. *tem*X (E.*tem') < O.*^htem-ʔ
 “dot, spot, point”
- (7) *diú* (H 665^m) 𦉑當各切，端鐸入一開
 M. *tak* (E.*tak) < O.*^htak
 “drip, drop”
 ⇔ *dī* (H 726^l) 𦉑都歷切，端錫入四開
 M. *tek* (E.*tejk) < O.*^htek
 “drop, drip”
- (8) *chēng* (M 15543) 撐丑庚切，徹庚平二開
 M. *trhæŋ* (E.*^hraŋjŋ) < O.*^hr-aŋ
 “post, pole, prop, strut”
 ⇔ *[zhən]* (834l) 𦉑陟盈切，知清平三開
 M. *trjeng* (E.*triaŋjŋ) < O.*^hr-eŋ
 “posts in framework, polet; terminal post”
- (9) *nǎng* (755^m) 𦉑奴郎切，泥蕩上一開
 M. *nang*X (E.*nan') < O.*^hnan-ʔ
 “muddy water”
 ⇔ *ning* (837g) 𦉑乃定切，泥徑去四開
 M. *nang*H (E.*neŋ^h) < O.*^hneŋ-s
 “mud; muddy, miry”
- rāng* (730f) 𦉑汝陽切，日陽平三開
 M. *nyang* (E.*niaŋ) < O.*^hnaŋ
 “heavy with dew; soaking”

2.1.3 LATERALS & RHOTICS (NON-NASAL RESONANTS)

(*l-, *hl-, *r-, *hr-)

- (10) *yì* (790c) 𦉑羊益切，以昔入三開
 M. *yek* (E.*jiajk) < O.*^hlak
 “be pleased, be pleasant”
 ⇔ *yì* (850a) 𦉑以鼓切，以贗去三開
 M. *yeh* (E.*jä^h) < O.*^hlek-s
 “easy, at ease; well-cultivated”
- (11) *yì* (790h) 𦉑羊益切，以昔入三開
 M. *yek* (E.*jiajk) < O.*^hlak
 “relay of horses; post-station”
 ⇔ *yì* (850a) 𦉑羊易切，以昔入三開
 M. *yek* (E.*jiajk) < O.*^hlek
 “change, exchange”
- yì* (790f) 𦉑羊益切，以昔入三開
 M. *yek* (E.*jiajk) < O.*^hlak
 “translate (exchange languages)”
 ⇔

- (12) *tāng* (725s) 堂徒郎切，定唐平一開
 M. *dang* (E.*dan) < O.*dan (? < *l-)
 “hall, main room”
 ⇨ M. *deng* (E.*deŋ) < O.*leŋ
 “court, courtyard”
- (13) *yuè* (1119f) 滄以灼切，以藥入三開
 M. *yak* (E.*jak) < O.*blawk
 “to shine; to melt”
 ⇨ M. *yemH* (E.*jiaw^h) < O. < *blawk-s
 “to shine, illuminate; bright”
 ⇨ *zhuó* (1124h) 濯直角切，澄覺入二開
 M. *dræwk* (E.*drawk) < O.*al-r-ewk
 “brilliant, fine; glossy”
 ⇨ *dí* (1120h) 的都歷切，端錫入四開
 M. *tek* (E.*tejk) < O.*al-lewk
 “bright, brilliant”
- (14) *zhuó* (795k) 斫之若切，章藥入三開
 M. *tsyak* (E.*tejak) < O.*ahlak
 “to chop, hack”
 ⇨ *hī* (850h) 剔他歷切，透錫入四開
 M. *thek* (E.*t^hejk) < O.*ahlak
 “to cut asunder; pick; separate meat from bone”
- (15) *liáng* (735a) 良呂張切，來陽平三開
 M. *liang* (E.*liang) < O.*bC-raŋ
 “good, fine”
 ⇨ M. *leng* (E.*leŋ) < O.*C-reŋ
 “numinous, divine, spirited, intelligent”
- (16) *cāng* (703e) 蒼七岡切，清唐平一開
 M. *tshang* (E.*t^han) < O.*a²s-hraŋ
 “dark green (vegetation), blue (sky), grey”
 ⇨ M. *tsheng* (E.*t^heng) < O.*a²s-hreŋ
 “green, blue, grey, black”
- (17) *cāng* (703c) 滄七岡切，清唐平一開
 M. *tshang* (E.*t^han) < O.*a²s-hraŋ
 “cold”
 ⇨ M. *tshengH* (E.*t^hen^h) < O.*b²s-hreŋ-s
 “cold”

2.1.4 DENTAL SIBILANTS

- (18) *jiè* (798u) 借子夜切，精禡去三開
 M. *tsjæ(k)H* (E.*tsia^h) < O.*b²tsAk-s
 “borrow, lend”
 ⇨ M. *tsreih* (E.*t^haij^h) < O.*a²ts-r-ek-s
 “debt”
- (19) *qián* (206c) 遷七然切，精仙平三開
 M. *tshjen* (E.*t^hian) < O.*b²tshan
 “move, transfer”
 ⇨ M. *dzen* (E.*dzen) < O.*adzen
 “before, ahead, preceding”

- (20) *ji* (798a) 籍秦音切，從昔入三開
 M. *dziək* (E.*dziajk) < O.*b^hdzak (?<*N-tsh-)
 “document, written record, register”
 ⇨ cè (845a) 冊楚革切，初麥入二開
 M. *tshək* (E.*tʂeijk) < O.*atsh-r-ek
 “writing tablet, register, document, volume”
 cè (868) 策楚革切，初麥入二開
 M. *tshək* (E.*tʂeijk) < O.*atsh-r-ek
 “writing tablet, plan”
- (21) *xiāng* (731a) 相息良切，心陽平三開
 M. *sjang* (E.*sjaŋ) < O.*b^hsaŋ
 ⇨ xǐng (812) 省息井切，心靜上三凱
 M. *sjeŋgX* (E.*siaŋʰ) < O.*b^hseŋʰ?
 “gaze, look, consider, inspect”
 “examine, watch, look”
- (22) *sǎn* (156a) 散蘇旱切，心旱上一開
 M. *sanX* (E.*sanʰ) < O.*a^hsan-ʔ
 ⇨ xián (156d) 霰蘇佃切，心霰去四腭
 M. *senH* (E.*senʰ) < O.*a^hsen-s
 “come loose, fall apart, scatter”
 “sleet”
- sǎn* (156a) 散蘇暉切，心翰去一開
 M. *sanH* (E.*sanʰ) < O.*a^hsan(?)^{-s}
 ⇨ xián (H 1691^v) 蘇佃切，心霰去四開
 M. *senH* (E.*senʰ) < O.*a^hs(K)en-s
 “break up, disperse (trans.), dispel”
 “sleet”

2.1.5 VELARS & LARYNGEALS

*k-, *kh-, *g-, *ŋ-, *hŋ-, *x-, *ʔ-

- (23) *gāng* (697a) 岡古郎切，見庚平一開
 M. *kang* (E.*kaŋ) < O.*b^hkaŋ
 ⇨ xīng (831l) 陞戶經切，匣青平四腭
 M. *heng* (E.*yejŋ) < O.*a^hgeŋ (?<*N-k-)
 “mountain ridge, hill”
 “ravine”
- (24) *jǐng* (755d) 景居影切，見梗上三開
 M. *kjaeŋgX* (E.*kiajŋʰ) < O.*A^hk-r-aŋ-ʔ
 ⇨ gēng (809a) 耿古辛切，見耿上三開
 M. *kejŋX* (E.*kəjŋʰ) < O.*b^hk-r-eŋ-ʔ
 “bright, splendid; reflection”
 “bright, brilliant; devoted”
- (25) *gāng* (697e) 綱古郎切，見唐平一開
 M. *kang* (E.*kaŋ) < O.*a^hkaŋ
 ⇨ jīng (831c) 經古靈切，見青平四開
 M. *keng* (E.*kejŋ) < O.*a^hkeŋ
 “string, tie, bond, guide-rope”
 “threads of a warp, main thread”
gēng (745f) 綆古杏切，見梗上二開
 M. *kaeŋgX* (E.*kəjŋʰ) < O.*a^hk-r-aŋ-ʔ
 ⇨ bīng (745f) 纒必郢切，幫靜上三開
 M. *pjiēŋX* (E.*pjiajŋʰ) < O.*b^hp-keŋ-ʔ
 “long rope, well-rope”
 “felly of a wheel (part which receives rope)”
- (26) *jiāng* (710c) 僵居良切，見陽平三開
 M. *kjang* (E.*kiaŋ) < O.*b^hkaŋ
 ⇨ qīng (828b) 傾去營切，溪清平三開
 M. *khjiwienɡ* (E.*k^hjiwjaŋ) < O.*b^hk^hw^heŋ
 “to fall down, prostrate”
 “to fall down, tumble, overturn”

- (27) *kāng* (746h) 康苦岡切，溪唐平一合
 M. *Khang* (E.*k^han) < O.*ak^han
 “prosperous, healthy, at ease”
qīng (753a) 慶丘敬切，溪映去三開
 M. *KhyæŋH* (E.*k^hiaŋ^h) < O.*b^hr^h-r-an-s
 “congratulate, celebrate”
 ⇔ *xìng* (810a) 幸胡耿切，匣耿上二開
 M. *heŋX* (E.*yeŋŋ[?]) < O.*ʔg-r-eŋ-ʔ
 “fortunate”
- (28) *qiáng* (713a) 強巨良切，群陽平三開
 M. *gjang* (E.*gjan) < O.*b^hgan (?<*N-k-)
 “strong, powerful”
jìng (754a) 競渠敬切，群映去三開
 M. *gjaŋŋH* (E.*giaŋŋ^h) < O.*b^hg-r-an-s
 “contend, struggle; zealous”
 ⇔ *jìng* (752c) 勁居正切，見勁去三開
 M. *kjiəŋH* (E.*kjian^h) < O.*b^hkeŋ-s
 “strong, vigorous”
- (29) *yì* (247b) 刈魚肺切，疑廢去三開
 M. *ŋjoŋH* (E.*ŋia^h) < O.*ŋat-s
 “to cut, mow”
niè (289g) 孽五結切，疑屑入四開
 M. *ŋjat* (E.*ŋiat) < O.*b^hŋ-r-at
 “retribution, punishment”
niè (289j) 孽魚列切，疑薛入三開
 M. *ŋat* (E.*ŋiat) < O.*b^hŋat
 “tree stump; new shoots from tree-stump”
 ⇔ *yì* (285h) | 剝牛例切，疑牒去三開
 M. *ŋjeŋH* (E.*ŋia^h) < O.*b^hŋ-r-et-s
 “to cut off the nose”
- (30) *xiāo* (1140a) 窻許嬌切，曉霽平三開
 M. *xjew* (E.*xiaw) < O.*b^hŋŋ-r-aw
 “clamour, noise”
dào (1130e) 嗷許幺切，曉蕭平四開
 M. *ngaw* (E.*ŋaw) < O.*a^hŋaw
 “distressed cry, be clamouring”
 ⇔ *xiào* (1164e) 曉五勞切，疑豪平一開
 M. *xew* (E.*xew) < O.*a^hŋew
 “be sounding with alarm; cry, make noise”
- (31) *xiāng* (717a) 香許良切，曉陽平三開
 M. *xjang* (E.*xian) < O.*b^hxan
 “fragrant”
 ⇔ *xīn/gǐ* (832f) 馨呼刑切，曉青平四開
 M. *xeng* (E.*xeŋŋ) < O.*a^hxen
 “fragrant”
- (32) *ān* (146a) 安烏寒切，影寒平一開
 M. *ʔan* (E.*ʔan) < O.*a^hʔan
 “peaceful, at ease, content”
 ⇔ *yàn* (146f) 晏烏旱切，影翰去一開
 M. *ʔenH* (E.*ʔan^h) < O.*a^hʔen-s
 “pleasant, at ease; clear, cloudless”

2.1.6 LABIOVELARS & -LARYNGEALS

(*k^w-, *kh^w-, *g^w-, *ŋ^w-, *hŋ^w-, *x^w-, *w-, *ʔ^w-)

- (33) *héng* (707m) 橫戶盲切，匣庚平二合
 M. *hwæŋ* (E.*ywaŋŋ) < O.*a_g^w-r-aŋ ⇨ M. *jiōng* (842d) 扃古螢切，見青平四合
 “crosswise, horizontal” (? < *N-k^w-) ⇨ M. *kweng* (E.*kweŋŋ) < O.*a_k^w-eŋ
 “bolt of a door, bar of a gate”
- héng* (748h) 衡戶庚切，匣庚平二開
 M. *hæŋ* (E.*yaiŋŋ) < O.*a_g-r-aŋ ⇨
- “crosswise; balance arm of steelyard, yoke”
- (34) *kuàng* (707n) 擴苦滂切，溪宕去一合 ⇨ *yíng* (843c) 瑩余傾切，以青平三合
 M. *khwanŋH* (E.*k^hwaŋ^h) < O.*a₁^hwaŋ-s ⇨ M. *yweng* (E.*jwiaŋŋ) < O.*b^wweŋ
 “grave, tomb, vault” (< *a₁kh-waŋ-s) “grave area, cemetery”
- (35) *yuè* (306h) 刖五刮切，疑轄入二合 ⇨ *yì* (285h) | 鼻 | 牛例切，疑際去三開
 M. *ŋwæt* (E.*ŋwaŋt) < O.*b^wŋ^w-r-at ⇨ M. *ŋjeŋH* (E.*ŋiaj^h) < O.*b^wŋ-r-et-s
 “cut off the feet, amputate” “to cut off the nose”
yuè (306h) 刖魚厥切，疑月入三合 ⇨ cf. (29)
 M. *ŋjwot* (E.*ŋuat) < O.*b^wŋ^w-at “cut off the feet, amputate”
- (36) ⇨ *qiōng* (843g|829a|829b|830a)
wáng (739t) 尨烏光切，影唐平一合 ⇨ 榮 | 惇 | | 孃渠光切，影唐平一合
 M. *ʔwanŋ* (E.*ʔwaŋ) < O.*a₂^ʔwaŋ ⇨ M. *gjiweng* (E.*gjwiaŋŋ) < O.*b^wg^weŋ
 “feeble, emaciated, crippled; depressed” “isolated, orphaned; depressed, helpless”
- (37) *wàng* (M 13774) 旺于放切，云滂去三合 ⇨ *yíng* (843a) 熒戶局切，匣青平四合
 M. *hjiwanŋH* (E.*wuaŋ^h) < O.*b^wwaŋ-s ⇨ M. *hweng* (E.*yweŋŋ) < O.*b^wweŋ
 “bright, shining” “glimmering, bright; dazzle”
 ⇨ *yíng* (843k) 瑩永兵切，云庚平三合
 M. *hjiwæŋ* (E.*wiaŋŋ) < O.*b^ww-r-eŋ
 “precious jadeite; lustrous, brilliant”

2.2 Attestation of OC final classes

- I. NONE (*-∅): *exx.* 5, 42, 43, 45, 48, 51, 53, 55, 61, 87
- II. LABIAL (*-p, *-m): *exx.* 6, 46, 60, 88, 93,
- III. DENTAL (*-t, *-n): *exx.* 19, 22, 29, 32, 35, 57, 62, 63, 65, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 74, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 89, 99
- IV. RHOTIC & APPROXIMANT (*-r, *-j [ʔ < *-l]): *exx.* 38, 39, 40, 50, 52, 59, 67, 79, 90
- V. VELAR (*-k, *-ŋ): *exx.* 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 31, 33, 34, 36, 37, 41, 44, 47, 49, 54, 56, 58, 66, 75, 76, 78, 86, 91, 92, 94, 95, 96, 97, 98, 100
- VI. LABIOVELAR (*-w, *-wk): *exx.* 13, 30, 64, 77

3. Some theoretical considerations

3.1 Feature matrix of OC vowels

FEATURE	[high]	[back]	[round]
*i	+	-	-
*ə	+	+	-
*u	+	+	+
*e	-	-	-
*o	-	+	+
*a	-	+	-

3.2 Distribution of WT vowel alternations throughout stem initial types: 36 / 50 (Simon 1974-75)

STEM INITIAL	GUTTURAL	PALATAL	DENTAL	LABIAL	R,L,H,Y'	FEATURES
X. 0 ⇔ u	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	[±hi]
I. a ⇔ e	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	[±bk]
III. a ⇔ o	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	[±rd]
IV. a ⇔ u	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	[±hi,rd]
VI. o ⇔ e	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	[±bk,rd]
IX. u ⇔ i		✓	✓	✓		[±bk,rd]
II. a ⇔ i			✓	✓	✓	[±hi,bk]
V. e ⇔ i			✓	✓		[±hi]
VIII. o ⇔ i		✓		✓		[±hi,bk,rd]
VII. e ⇔ u		✓				[±hi,bk,rd]

3.3 Theoretically possible vowel alternations in a six-vowel system and their implied feature distances (1-3): 15 ⇔ types (30 ⇔ types, i.e. including directionality)

VOWEL	*i	*ə	*u	*e	*o	*a
*i	•	0	1	2	1	3
*ə	<u>*i</u> ⇔ *ə	•	0	1	2	2
*u	<u>*i</u> ⇔ *u	*ə ⇔ *u	•	0	3	1
*e	*i ⇔ *e	*ə ⇔ *e	*u ⇔ *e	•	0	2
*o	<u>*i</u> ⇔ *o	*ə ⇔ *o	*u ⇔ *o	*e ⇔ *o	•	0
*a	<u>*i</u> ⇔ *a	*ə ⇔ *a	*u ⇔ *a	<u>*e</u> ⇔ *a	*o ⇔ *a	•

unmarked apophonic directionality?

3.4 Baxter's OC vowel system (1992, 1995)

MAIN VOWEL/ CODA	*i	*ə	*u	*e	*a	*o
*-∅	(-i>-ij) 幽 _B	之	幽 _A	支	魚	侯
*-w	幽 _B	×	×	宵 _A	宵 _B	×
*-k	(-ik>-ii) 覺 _B	職	覺 _A	錫	鐸	屋
*-wk	覺 _B	×	×	藥 _A	藥 _B	×
*-j	脂	微 _A	微 _B	(歌 _A)	歌 _B	歌 _C
*-t	質	物 _A	物 _B	月/祭 _A	月/祭 _B	月/祭 _C
*-n	眞	文 _A	文 _B	元 _A	元 _B	元 _C
*-r	×	文 _C	?文 _D	×	元 _D	×
*-ŋ	(-iŋ>-im) 侵 _A	蒸	冬	耕	陽	東
*-m	侵 _A	侵 _B	?侵 _C	談 _A	談 _B	?談 _C
*-p	緝 _A	緝 _B	?緝 _C	盍 _A	盍 _B	?盍 _C

4. Possible ablaut types in OC: 107 + *15 (disregarding apophonic directionality) + some examples

4.1 *a ⇨ *ə, [ɛhigh]: 8

(元_B ⇨ 文_A • 月_B ⇨ 物_A • 歌_B ⇨ 微_A • 魚 ⇨ 之 • 鐸 ⇨ 職 • 陽 ⇨ 蒸 • 談_B ⇨ 侵_B • 盍_C ⇨ 緝_B)

- (38) *mǐ* (17h) 靡文彼切，明紙上三開 ⇨ *wēi* (584d) 微無非切，微微平三合
 M. *mjɛX* (E.*miǎ') < O.*m(-r)-aj-ʔ ⇨ M. *mji* (E.*muǐ) < O.*b₁mɛj
 “small, extravagant; NEG: ‘there is not’” ⇨ “small, minute; NEG: ‘were it not for’”
- (39) *huǐ* (356a) 毀許委切，曉紙上三合 ⇨ *huō* (353a) 火呼果切，曉果上一合
 M. *xjwɛX* (E.xwiǎ') < O.^hhm(-r)-aj-ʔ ⇨ M. *xwax* (E.*xwa') < O.*^hhmɛj-ʔ
 “destroy, defame” ⇨ “fire”
- (40) *huǐ* (17i) 麾許爲切，曉支平三合 ⇨ *huī* (584h) 徽許歸切，曉微平三合
 M. *xjwɛ* (E.*xwiǎ) < O.*^hhmaj ⇨ M. *xjwɛj* (E.*xuǐ) < O.*^hhmɛj
 “to signal with a flag; command; flag” ⇨ “signalize, display; flag, emblem”
- (41) *dǎng* (725r) 黨多郎切，端蕩上一開 ⇨ *děng* (961') 等多肯切，端等上一開
 M. *tangX* (E.*taŋ') < O.*^ataŋ-ʔ ⇨ M. *tongX* (E.*taŋ') < O.*^ataŋ-ʔ
 “party, class, village of 50 people, partisan” ⇨ “class, rank, grade; equal”
- (42) *zhì* (45n') 置陟慮切，知御去三合 ⇨ *zhì* (919g) 置陟吏切，知志去三開
 M. *driəH* (E.*triǎ^h) < O.*^bd-r-a-s (? < *N-t-) ⇨ M. *triH* (E.*tri^h) < O.*^bl-r-a-s < -ak-s
 “place, position, order; appear; visible” ⇨ “place, set; set aside, rest”
- (43) *chù* (45l) 儲直魚切，澄於平三合 ⇨ *zhì* (961s) 痔直里切，澄止上三開
 M. *driə* (E.*driǎ) < O.*^bd-r-a ⇨ M. *driX* (E.*dri') < O.*^bd-r-a-ʔ
 “store up, collect; heir to the throne” ⇨ “to accumulate, store; provide”
- (44) *náng* (370k) 囊奴當切，泥唐平一開 ⇨ *réng* (945e) 仍如乘切，日蒸平三開
 M. *nang* (E.*naŋ) < O.*^anaŋ ⇨ M. *nying* (E.*niŋ) < O.*^bnaŋ
 “formerly, of old” ⇨ “as before, still, yet; repeatedly”
- (45) *yǐ* (83a|89b) 子與餘呂切，以語上三合 ⇨ *yí* (976x) 貽與之切，以之平三開
 M. *yoX* (E.*jiǎ') < O.*^bla-ʔ ⇨ M. *yí* (E.*ji) < O.*^ble
 “give” ⇨ “bestow, hand down, give”
- (46) *tán* (617l) 談徒甘切，定談平一開 ⇨ *tán* (646c) 譚徒含切，定覃平一開
 M. *dam* (E.*dam) < O.*lām ⇨ M. *dom* (E.*dam) < O.*al[e,u]m
 “talk, chat; discussion” ⇨ “talk (about)”

- (47) *shè* (807a) 射神夜切，船禡去三開
 M. *zyæH* (E.**zia^h*) < O. **b^hm-lAk-s*
 “to shoot with bow & arrow”
shì (790I) 釋施隻切，書昔入三開
 M. *syek* (E.**ciajk*) < O. **b^hhlak*
 “release, unloose, detach”
 ⇔
yì (918a) 弋與職切，以職入三開
 M. *yik* (E.**jik*) < O. **b^hlak*
 shoot with arrow & string
- (48) *xù* (45s) 緒徐呂切，邪語上三合
 M. *joX* (E.**siä’*) < O. **b^hza-ʔ* < **b^hs-da-ʔ*
 “thread, sequence,
xù (83h) 序徐呂切，邪語上三合
 M. *zjoX* (E.**ziä’*) < O. **b^hzla-ʔ* < **b^hs-la-ʔ*
 “order, arrange in order; school”
 ⇔
sì (972k) 嗣許吏切，邪志去三開
 M. *zih* (E.**zi^h*) < O. **b^hzə-s* < **b^hs-hlə-s*
 “succeed, succession, heir”
- (49) *luò* (766r) 盧各切，來鐸入一開
 M. *lak* (E.**lak*) < O. **Ak-r-ak*
 “raw skin, animal hide”
 ⇔
gé (931a) 革古核切，見麥入二開
 M. *kek* (E.**kejik*) < O. **Ak-r-ək*
 “animal hide, skin, reins”
- (50) *yǐ* (2x) 蟻於倚切，疑紙上三開
 M. *ngjex* (E.**giä’*) < O. **ŋ(-r)-aj-ʔ*
 “ant”
 ⇔
yǐ (548i) 螳於倚切，疑紙上三開
 M. *ngjix* (E.**gij’*) < O. **b^hgej-ʔ*
 “ant”
- (51) *ài* (956g) 礙五漑切，疑代去一開
 M. *nojH* (E.**nej^h*) < O. **a^hŋə-s*
 “obstruct, block up, impede”
 ⇔
wú (60g) 迂五故切，疑墓去一合
 M. *ŋuH* (E.**ŋə^h*) < O. **a^hŋə-s*
 “go against, oppose”
- ài* (937t) 五漑切，疑代去一開
 M. *nojH* (E.**nej^h*) < O. **a^hŋə-s*
 “obstruct, block up, impede”
 ⇔
wú (60g) 忤五故切，疑墓去一合
 M. *ŋuH* (E.**ŋə^h*) < O. **a^hŋə-s*
 “opposed, refractory”
- wù* (768d) 蓋五故切，疑墓去一合
 M. *ŋuH* (E.**ŋə^h*) < O. **a^hŋə(k)-s*
 “oppose, resist”
- (52) *yǐ* (1F) 倚於綺切，影紙上三開
 M. *ʒjex* (E.**ʒiä’*) < O. **b^hʔ(-r)-aj-ʔ*
 “lean on, rely on”
 ⇔
yǐ (550a) 依於希切，影微平三開
 M. *ʒij* (E.**ʒij*) < O. **b^hʔəj*
 “lean on, depend on”

- (53) *gũ* (49a) 古 公戶切，見姥上一合
 M. *kuX* (E.*kɔʼ) < O.*^{ak}a-ʔ
 “olden times, former times; old”
gũ (49i) 故 古暮切，見暮去一合
 M. *kuH* (E.*kɔʰ) < O.*^{ak}a(ʔ)-s
 “former, old friend; precedent, reason for”
 ⇨ *jiũ* (993a) 久 舉有切，見有上三合
 M. *kjuwX* (E.*kuwʼ) < O.*^{bk}w-a-ʔ
 “for a long time, long-lasting”
- (54) *guǎng* (797b) 廣 古晃切，見蕩上一合
 M. *kangX* (E.*kwaŋʼ) < O.*^{ak}w-aŋ-ʔ
 “wide, broad, vast”
 ⇨ *hóng* (887g) 弘 胡耿切，匣登平一合
 M. *hwong* (E.*ywaŋ) < O.*^{ag}w-aŋ
 “great, vast”
- (55) *x/qũ* (78b) 墟 去魚切，溪魚平三合
 M. *khjo* (E.*kʰiä) < O.*^{bk}h(-r)-a
 “mound, large hill, site of ruined city”
 ⇨ *qiu* (994a) 丘 去鳩切，溪尤平三開
 M. *khjuw* (E.*kʰuɰ) < O.*^{bk}w-hə
 “mound, hillock, grave; empty”
- (56) *wǎng* (739a) 枉 紆往切，影滂上三合
 M. *?jwangX* (E.*?uaŋʼ) < O.*^{bp}?-aŋ-ʔ
 “bent, crooked”
 ⇨ *gōng* (901a) 弓 居成切，見東平三合
 M. *kjuwng* (E.*kuwŋ) < O.*^{bk}w-aŋ
 “bow”
 ⇨ *gōng* (887f) 肱 古弘切，見登平一合
 M. *kwong* (E.*kwaŋ) < O.*^{ak}w-aŋ
 “elbow, upper arm”
- (57) *yue* (204a) 曰 王伐切，云月入三合
 M. *hjuot* (E.*wuat) < O.*^bwat
 “to say; be called”
 ⇨ *wèi* (523d) 謂 于貴切，云謂去三合
 M. *hwjH* (E.*wuɰʰ) < O.*^bwat-s
 “to speak to, mean, call”
 ⇨ *huà* (302o) 話 下快切，匣月去二合
 M. *hwæH* (E.*ywaɰʰ) < O.*^{ag}w-r-at-s
 “speech, talk”
 (? < O.*^{Nk}w-r-at-s)

4.2 *o ⇨ *u, [±high]: 8

(元c ⇨ 文B • 月c ⇨ 物B • 歌c ⇨ 微B • 侯 ⇨ 幽A • 屋 ⇨ 覺A • 東 ⇨ 冬 • 談c ⇨ 侵c • 霰c ⇨ 緝c)

- (58) *dǒng* (1175f) 凍 多貢切，端送去一合
 M. *tuwngh* (E.*tawŋʰ) < O.*^{at}oŋ-s
 ⇨ *dōng* (1002a) 冬 都宗切，端冬平一合
 M. *towng* (E.*taɰŋ) < O.*^{at}uŋ
 “to freeze”
 ⇨ *tu* (544a) 賸 杜回切，定灰平一合
 M. *dwɔj* (E.*dwaɰ) < O.*^{at}uj
 “collapse, fall down, give way”
 “fall”
 ⇨ “fall”
 “collapse, fall down, give way”

4.3 *e ⇨ *ə, [ɛhigh]/[ɛback]: 6

(元A ⇨ 文A • 支 ⇨ 之 • 錫 ⇨ 職 • 耕 ⇨ 蒸 • 談A ⇨ 侵B • 盍A ⇨ 緝B)

- (60) *dián* (618n) 點多忝切，端忝上四開 ⇨ *dǎn* (656n) 黠都感切，端感上一開
M. *temX* (E.*tem') < O.*atem-? ⇨ M. *tonX* (E.*tə/am-?) < O.*[tə,u]m-?
“dot, spot, point” ⇨ “dirt, dregs, black”
- (61) *dī* (870e) 遞特計切，定霽去四開 ⇨ *dài* (918i) 代徒耐切，定代去一開
M. *deɪH* (E.*de:jʰ) < O.*a1e(k)-s ⇨ M. *doɪH* (E.*də:jʰ) < O.*a1a(k)-s
“substitute, alternate” ⇨ “substitute, replace”

4.4 *a ⇨ *i [ɛhigh]/[ɛback]: 7 + ?3

(元B ⇨ 眞 • 月B ⇨ 質 • 歌B ⇨ 脂 • 霽B ⇨ 幽B • 藥B ⇨ 覺 • 談B ⇨ 侵A • 盍B ⇨ 緝A || ?魚 ⇨ 脂 • ?鐸 ⇨ 質 • ?陽 ⇨ 眞)

- (62) *fa* (275c) 發方伐切，非月入三合 ⇨ *bī* (407i) 弭畢吉切，幫至入三開
M. *pjot* (E.*puat) < O.*^bpat ⇨ M. *pjit* (E.*pjit) < O.*^bpit
“to shoot an arrow; send out, emit” ⇨ “to shoot an arrow”
- (63) *dǎn* (148a) 豈多旱切，端旱上一開 ⇨ *zhēn* (375a) 真職鄰切，章真平三開
M. *tanX* (E.*tan') < O.*^atan ⇨ M. *tsyin* (E.*tɕin) < O.*^btin
“sincere, -ly, -ity” ⇨ “true, real, sincere”
- (64) *dāo* (1131a) 刀都牟切，端豪平一開 ⇨ *dāo* (1083rit) 彫 | 雕都聊切，端蕭平四開
M. *taw* (E.*taw) < O.*^ataw ⇨ M. *tew* (E.*tew) < O.*^atiw
“knife” ⇨ “carve, engrave, incise”
- (65) *liè* (291b) 冽良靴切，來薛入三開 ⇨ *lì* (H 126^m) 漑力質切，來質入三開
M. *liet* (E.*liat) < O.*^bC-rat ⇨ M. *lit* (E.*lit) < O.*^bC-rit
“cold” ⇨ “cold”
- (66) *liang* (735a) 良呂張切，來陽平三開 ⇨ *ling* (823a) 令力政切，來勁去三開
M. *liang* (E.*liang) < O.*^bC-ran ⇨ M. *liengH* (E.*lianjʰ) < O.*^bC-rin-s
“good, fine” ⇨ “good, fine, quick-witted”
- (67) *shī* (41') 施式支切，書支平三開 ⇨ *shī* (561a) 尸式脂切，書脂平三開
M. *syē* (E.*ɕiə) < O.*^ahaj ⇨ M. *syij* (E.*ɕi) < O.*^bhij
“spread, bestow, grant” ⇨ “set forth, expose; act for spirit in sacrifice”
- (68) *lā* (271d) 撻他大切，透曷入一開 ⇨ *chī* (H 778^m) 扶丑栗切，徹至入三開
M. *that* (E.*tʰat) < O.*^ahlat ⇨ M. *thit* (E.*tʰrit) < O.*^bhl-rit
“beat, flog, whip” ⇨ “beat, flog”

- (69) *qiān* (206c) 遷七然切，精仙平三開
 M. *tshjen* (E.*tʂʰian) < O.*bʰshan
 “move, transfer” ⇨ *jìn* (379a) 進即刃切，精震去三開
 M. *tsjinH* (E.*tsinʰ) < O.*bʰsin-s
 “advance, move forth; introduce?”
- (70) *jié* (313p) 偈渠列切，群薛入三開
 M. *gjet* (E.*gial) < O.*bʰg-r-at
 “heroic, strong; hero” ⇨ M. *Khet* (E.*kʰait) < O.*akh-r-it
 “with all one’s strength, firmly”
- jié* (284b) 傑渠列切，群薛入三開
 M. *gjet* (E.*gial) < O.*bʰg-r-at
 “heroic, strong; hero” ⇨
- (71) *yàn* (H 1522ʳ) 贗五晏切，疑諫去二開
 M. *ngæŋH* (E.*ŋainʰ) < O.*ʰŋ-r-an-s
 ⇨ *yín* (1251a) 嚚語巾切，疑眞平三開
 M. *gin* (E.*gin) < O.*bʰŋ-r-in (? < *bʰN-k-r-in)
 “counterfeit, spurious, deceitful” ⇨ M. *gin* (E.*ʔinʰ) < O.*bʰʔit-s
 “insincere, stupid”
- (72) *ài* (313y) 餽於麗切，影祭去三開
 M. *ʒjeH* (E.*ʒiaʰ) < O.*bʰʔat-s
 ⇨ *yì* (395h) 饑乙冀切，影至去三開
 M. *ʒiH* (E.*ʒiʰ) < O.*bʰʔit-s
 “spoiled food, sour food” ⇨ “spoiled food, tainted food”
- (73) *àn* (146d) 按烏旱切，影旱去一開
 M. *ʒanH* (E.*ʒanʰ) < O.*ʒan-s
 ⇨ *yàn* (1251f) 印於刃切，影震去三開
 M. *ʒinH* (E.*ʒinʰ) < O.*bʰʒin-s
 “press down, lay hand on; fix” ⇨ “to seal, stamp, print; seal”
- (74) *huàn* (167c) 煥火貫切，曉換去一合
 M. *xwanH* (E.*xwanʰ) < O.*ʰhwan-s
 ⇨ *xuàn* (392r) 絢許縣切，曉霰去四合
 M. *xwenH* (E.*xwenʰ) < O.*ʰwin-s
 “bright, shining” ⇨ “gorgeous, patterned, decorated”

4.5 *a ⇨ *u, [±high]/[±round]: 8

(元_B ⇨ 文_B • 月_B ⇨ 物_B • 歌_B ⇨ 微_B • 魚 ⇨ 幽_A • 鐸 ⇨ 覺 • 陽 ⇨ 冬 • 談_B ⇨ 侵_B • 盍 ⇨ 緝_B)

- (75) *mù* (802o) 慕慕各切，明鐸入一開
 M. *mak* (E.*mak) < O.*a²mak
 ⇨ *mào* (1062a) 冒莫報切，明號去一開
 M. *mawH* (E.*mawʰ) < O.*a²muk-s
 “veil, curtain, cover” ⇨ “to cover; covering; cover”
- (76) *rǎng* (730d) 壤如兩切，日養上三開
 M. *nyangX* (E.*ŋiaŋʰ) < O.*bʰnaŋ-ʔ
 ⇨ *nóng* (1005a) 農如冬切，泥冬平一合
 M. *nowng* (E.*nawŋ) < O.*a²nuŋ
 “fertile soil, arable soil, loam” ⇨ “to work on soil; agriculture; peasant”

- (77) *gāo* (1129a) 高古勞切，見豪平一開
 M. *kaw* (E.**kaw*) < O.**akaw* ⇨ M. *gāo* (1040a) 皋古勞切，見豪平一開
 “high” ⇨ M. *kaw* (E.**kaw*) < O.**akw*
 “high; marsh”
- (78) *suó* (770a) 索蘇各切，心鐸入一開
 M. *sak* (E.**sak*) < O.**sak* ⇨ *sū* (1029c) 縮所六切，生屋入三合
 “twist a rope; bind; cord, cable” ⇨ M. *stjuwk* (E.**suwk*) < O.**b_s-r-uk*
 “bind together; tie”
 ? *shu* (1222a) 束書玉切，書濁入三合
 M. *syowk* (E.**quawk*) < **s-tok*
 “tie in a bundle”

4.6 *e ⇨ *i, [ɛhigh]/[±round]: 6 + ?3

(元_A ⇨ 眞 • 月_A ⇨ 質 • 霄_A ⇨ 幽_B • 藥_A ⇨ 覺_B • 談_A ⇨ 侵_A • 盍_A ⇨ 緝_A || ?支 ⇨ 脂 • ?錫 ⇨ 質 • ?耕 ⇨ 眞)

- (79) *zhé* (638a) 曄之涉切，章葉入三開
 M. *tsyep* (E.**teiap*) < O.**b_t-nep* ⇨ *zhé* (685h) 惹之入切，章緝入三開
 “to fear, be afraid, paralyzed” ⇨ M. *tsyip* (E.**tcip*) < O.**b_t-nip*
 “to fear, be afraid, paralyzed”
- (80) *xuán* (236a) 旋似宣切，邪仙平三合
 M.**ziwen* (E.**zwien*) < O.**b_N-swen* ⇨ *xún* (392e) 徇詳會切，邪，諄平三合
 “revolve, spin, whirl” ⇨ M. *zwin* (E.**zwin*) < O.**b_N-swin*
 “all around, everywhere; follow”
- (81) *jié* (310b) 截昨結切，從屑入四開
 M. *dzet* (E.**dzet*) < O.**a_dzet* (? < **a_N-tsh^h*) ⇨ *qiè* (400f) 切千結切，精屑入四開
 “revolve, rotate” ⇨ M. *tshet* (E.**tsh^het*) < O.**a_tshit*
 “cut, splice”
 ⇨ *jié* (399c) 節子結切，精屑入四開
 “section, joint, juncture”
 ⇨ M. *tset* (E.**tset*) < O.**a_tsit* < **a_tsik*
 “section, joint, juncture”
- (82) *qián* (196e) 錢去演切，溪獮上三開
 M. *khiyenX* (E.**k^hjian[’]*) < O.**b_khen-?* ⇨ *jīn* (368g) 緊居刃切，見軫上三開
 “closely attached; to cling to” ⇨ M. *kinX* (E.**kjin[’]*) < O.**b_kkin-?* (? < **N-kin-?*)
 “tie tightly; tense taut, tight”
- (83) *xian* (1250e) 晁胡典切，匣銑上四開
 M. *hen* (E.**yen[’]*) < O.**a_{gen}* ⇨ *xuán* (366h) 炫黃練切，匣霰去四合
 “sunlight” ⇨ M. *henH* (E.**ywen^h*) < O.**a_{gin}-s*
 “brightness, sunshine; bright”

- (84) *jué* (496s) 掘衝物切，群物入三合 ⇨ *xué* (409a) 穴胡決切，匣曆入四合
 M. *gyut* (E.**guat*) < O.**b*g[e,u]t ⇨ M. *hwet* (E.**ywet*) < O.**a*g^wit
 “dig out” ⇨ “cave, cavern, grotto”
- (85) *xiam* (209a) 鮮相然切，心佃平三開 ⇨ *xim* (382k) 新息鄰切，新眞平三開
 M. *sjen* (E.**sian*) < O.**b*sen (?< **b*ser) ⇨ M. *sin* (E.**sin*) < O.**b*sin
 “fresh” ⇨ “new”

4.7 *o ⇨ *a, [ɛhigh]/[ɛround]: 8

- (元c ⇨ 文_A ⇨ 物_A • 月c ⇨ 物_A • 歌c ⇨ 微_B • 侯 ⇨ 之 • 屋 ⇨ 職 • 東 ⇨ 蒸 • 談c ⇨ 侵_B • 盍c ⇨ 緝_B)
- (86) *lóng* (1193f) 壘力腫切，來腫上三合 ⇨ *ling* (898c) 陵力膺切，來蒸平三開
 M. *ljowngX* (E.**luawŋ*’) < O.**B*C-roy-ʔ ⇨ M. *ling* (E.**liŋ*) < O.**b*-raŋ
 “grave mound; ridge in a field” ⇨ “mound, tomb, grave; ascend upon”

4.8 *e ⇨ *u, [ɛhigh]/[ɛback]/[ɛround]: 8

- (元_A ⇨ 文_B • 月_A ⇨ 物_B • 支 ⇨ 幽_A • 錫 ⇨ 覺_A • 耕 ⇨ 冬 • 幫_A ⇨ 幽_A • 談_A ⇨ 侵_C • 盍_A ⇨ 緝_C)
- (87) *di* (877j) 締特計切，定霽去四開 ⇨ *chou* (1083m) 綢直由切，澄尤平三開
 M. *dejH* (E.**dej^h*) < O.**a*de ⇨ M. *djuw* (E.**druw*) < O.**b*d-r-u
 “to tie, knot, bind” ⇨ “wind around, wrap”

4.9 *o ⇨ *i, [ɛhigh]/[ɛback]/[ɛround]: 5 + ʔ3

(元c ⇨ 眞 • 月c ⇨ 質 • 歌c ⇨ 脂 • 談c ⇨ 侵_A • 盍c ⇨ 緝_A || ʔ侯 ⇨ 脂 • ʔ屋 ⇨ 脂 • ʔ東 ⇨ 眞)
 no sufficient amount of examples available!

4.10 *ə ⇨ *i, [ɛback]: 5 + ʔ3

文_A ⇨ 眞 • 物_A ⇨ 質 • 微_A ⇨ 眞 • 侵_B ⇨ 侵_A • 緝_B ⇨ 緝_A || ʔ之 ⇨ 脂 • ʔ職 ⇨ 質 • ʔ蒸 ⇨ 眞

- (88) *tan* (646b) 潭徒含切，定覃平一腭 ⇨ *chen* (656b) 沈直深切，澄侵平三開
 M. *dom* (E.**dam*) < O.**a*lam ⇨ M. *drim* (E.**drim*) < O.**b*l-r-im
 “deep pool, deep (of water)” ⇨ “sink into water, drown, submerge”
- dān* (658l) 湛丁含切，端覃一開 ⇨
 M. *tom* (E.**ta*) < O.**a*-lam ⇨
 “sunk in, steeped in (pleasure)” ⇨
shen (666c) 深式針切，書侵平三開 ⇨
 M. *syim* (E.**gim*) < O.**b*hlam ⇨
 “deep”

zhàn (6581) 湛徒減切，澄賺上二開
M. *dremX* (E. *dramʔ) < O. *ʔN-k-ɬəm-ʔ ⇨

“to sink in water, drown; deep water”

(89) *jiān* (368c) 堅古賢切，見先平四開
M. *ken* (E. *ken) < O. *ʔkin ⇨ M. *ken* (E. *kəin) < O. *ʔk-r-an

“hard, solid”

“hard (of soil), hard difficult”

(90) *āi* (938b) 埃烏開切，影哈平一開

M. *ʔoj* (E. *ʔej) < O. *ʔʔej ⇨

yī 豎烏奚切，影齊平四開

M. *ʔej* (E. *ʔej) < O. *ʔʔij

“dust, dirt”

“dust, dirt; haze”

4.11 *a ⇨ *e, [ʔback]: 9,

(元_B ⇨ 元_A • 月_B ⇨ 月_A • 魚 ⇨ 支 • 鐸 ⇨ 錫 • 陽 ⇨ 耕 • 霽_B ⇨ 霽_A • 藥_B ⇨ 藥_A • 談_B ⇨ 談_A • 盍_B ⇨ 盍_A)

cf. 2.1 for examples

4.12 *u ⇨ *i, [ʔback]/[ʔround]: 5 + ʔ3

(文_B ⇨ 眞 • 物_B ⇨ 質 • 微_B ⇨ 脂 • 侵_C ⇨ 侵_A • 緝_C ⇨ 緝_A || ʔ幽_A ⇨ 脂 • ʔ覺 ⇨ 質 • ʔ冬 ⇨ 眞)

no sufficient amount of examples available!

4.13 *o ⇨ *e, [ʔback]/[ʔround]: 7

(元_C ⇨ 元_A • 月_C ⇨ 月_A • 侯 ⇨ 支 • 屋 ⇨ 錫 • 東 ⇨ 耕 • 談_C ⇨ 談_A • 盍_C ⇨ 盍_A)

(91) *lǎng* (1180a) 弄盧貢切，來送去一合
M. *luwŋH* (E. *luwŋ^h) < O. *ʔC-roŋ-s ⇨ *ling* (823g) 伶郎丁切，來青平四開

“play, play with, handle”

M. *leŋ* (E. *leŋ) < O. *ʔC-reŋ

“actor, musician”

(92) *zhuó* (1235b) 斲竹角切，知覺入二開

M. *træwǎk* (E. *traik) < O. *ʔt-r-ok ⇨

tī (850h) 剔他歷切，透錫入四開

M. *thək* (E. *t^hejk) < O. *ʔ^hlek

“to chop, hew, hack”

(? < *N-lr-ʔ)

“to cut asunder, pick; separate meat from bone”

(93) *hé* (675a) 合侯關切，匣合入一開

M. *hop* (E. *ya/ap) < *ʔgop (? < *N-k-) ⇨

xié (693b/c) 協|叶胡頰切，匣帖入四開

M. *hep* (E. *yep) < O. *ʔq[*i*,e]p

“be joined together”

“in cooperation with, jointly”

gé (675a) 合古沓切，見合入一開

M. *kop* (E. *kə/ap) < *ʔkop ⇨

“join, bring together”

hé (642n) 盍胡臘切，匣蓋入一開
 M. *hap* (E.*yap) < O. *ʔ²gop (? < *N-k-) ⇨
 “join, unite”

hé (642s) 闔胡臘切，匣蓋入一開
 M. *hap* (E.*yap) < O. *ʔ²gop (? < *N-k-) ⇨
 “to shut; leaf of a door”

?
hui (321a) 會黃外切，匣泰去一合
 M. *hwajH* (E.ywajh) < O. *ʔ²gwaj-s < *-p-s ⇨
 “unite, collect, meet, come together”

(94) *kōng* (1172b) 空苦紅切，溪東平三合
 M. *khuwng* (E.*kʰəwŋ) < O. *ʔ¹kʰoŋ ⇨
 “empty, hollow, in vain; sky”
qìng (832d) 罄 | 苦定切，溪徑去四開
 M. *khengH* (E.*kʰeɲh) < O. *ʔ¹kʰeŋ-s

(95) *yōng* (1184i) 壅於隴切，影鐘上三合
 M. *ʔiowŋX* (E.*ʔuawŋ) < O. *bʔ(-r)oŋ-ʔ ⇨
 “exhausted, depleted, empty; exhaustively”
yīng (814d) 瘵於郢切，影靜上三開
 M. *ʔiəwŋX* (E.*ʔiaɲh) < O. *bʔ(-r)eŋ-ʔ
 “swelling, goitre, tumour, gall”

(96) *wèng* (1185p) 甕烏貢切，滂送去一合
 M. *ʔuwŋH* (E.*ʔəwŋh) < O. *ʔ²oŋg-s ⇨
 “jug, jar, pitcher”
yīng (814hM 21620) 嬰 | 嬰烏莖切，影耕平二開
 M. *ʔeŋ* (E.*ʔeiŋ) < O. *ʔ²-r-əŋg
 “small mouthed jar, jug”

yōng (1185o) 饜於容切，影鐘平三合
 M. *ʔiowŋ* (E.*ʔuawŋ) < O. *bʔ(-r)oŋ ⇨
 “jug, jar, pitcher”

4.14 *u ⇨ *ə, [±round]: 9

(文_B ⇨ 文_A • 文_D ⇨ 文_C • 物_B ⇨ 物_A • 微_B ⇨ 微_A • 幽 ⇨ 之 • 覺_A ⇨ 職 • 冬 ⇨ 蒸 • 侵_C ⇨ 侵_B • 緇_C ⇨ 緇_B)

no sufficient amount of examples available!

4.15 *a ⇨ *o, [±round]: 8

(元_B ⇨ 元_C • 月_B ⇨ 月_C • 歌_B ⇨ 歌_C • 魚 ⇨ 侯 • 鐸 ⇨ 屋 • 陽 ⇨ 東 • 談_B ⇨ 談_C • 盍_B ⇨ 盍_C)

(97) *máng* (742q) 盲武庚切，明庚平二開
 M. *mæŋ* (E.*maiŋ) < O. *ʔ²m-r-aŋ
 “blind”
méng (1181c) 朦莫紅切，明東平一合
 M. *muwng* (E.*məwŋ) < O. *ʔ²mɔŋg
 “blind, dizzy”

- (98) *zhàng* (M 29570) 脹知亮切，知漾去三開 ⇔ *zhōng* (1188e) 腫之隴切，之漾上三開
 M. *trjangH* (E.**trjaŋʰ*) < O.**b^h-r-aŋ-s* ⇔ M. *tsyowŋgX* (E.**tɕuawŋʷ*) < O.**b^htoŋ-ʔ*
 “to swell, expand; be bloated” ⇔ “swollen; swelling, tumour”
- (99) *yǎn* (252h) 臃魚羣切，疑牀上三開 ⇔ *yuan* (257a) 元愚袁切，影元平三合
 M. *ngjenzX* (E.**gianʷ*) < O.**b^hŋ(-r)-an-ʔ* ⇔ M. *ngjwon* (E.**guan*) < O.**b^hŋon*
 “top, summit” ⇔ “head, principal part; supreme”
guan (160a) 冠古丸切，見桓平一合
 ⇔ M. *kwan* (E.**kwan*) < O.**a^hk-ŋon*
 “cap, hat”
- (100) *wò* (1141i) 沃烏酷切，影沃入一合 ⇔ *w/ò, ù* (1204g) 渥於角切，影覺入二開
 M. *ʔowk* (E.**ʔawk*) < O.**a^hʔawk* ⇔ M. *ʔæwk* (E.**ʔaiwk*) < O.**a^hʔ-r-ok*
 “to soak, moisten, irrigate” ⇔ “to soak, moisten; soaking”

5. Frequency of ablaut types:

- I. *a ⇔ *e, [±back] >> *a ⇔ *ə, [±high] >> *a ⇔ *i [±high]/[±back]
 II. *a ⇔ *u, [±high]/[±round], *e ⇔ *i, [±high]/[±round], *o ⇔ *e >> [±back]/[±round] >>
 *a ⇔ *o, [±round] >> *ə ⇔ *i, [±back]
 III. *o ⇔ *u, [±high], *e ⇔ *ə, [±high]/[±back], *o ⇔ *ə, [±high]/[±round],
 *e ⇔ *u, [±high]/[±back]/[±round]
 IV. *u ⇔ *ə, [±round], *u ⇔ *i, [±back]/[±round], *o ⇔ *i, [±high]/[±back]/[±round]

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